

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND DIGITALIZATION IN HISTORICAL RETROSPECT

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Abstract: The article presents the author's concept of the digital economy as a scientific direction (digital economics), focused on the study of the fundamental causes and consequences of the digital transformation of the real economy, increasing the share of digital products and services in it, as well as new forms of business based on digital technologies (digital economy). The fundamental properties of information presented in digital format on various media (electronic, optical, mechanical, etc.) are noted. Their manifestations in the real economy are shown. The historical continuity of the idea of digitalization of the economy and culture as a whole, the gradual displacement of analog technologies and devices by their digital substitutes with the development and cheapening of digital technologies is traced (indicating key dates and events). Connections and intersections with related scientific fields, including knowledge economics, information economics and knowledge management, are noted.

Key words: additive technologies, digitization, digital format, idempotent addition, sampling theorem, transaction costs

1. Introduction

The appeal to the history of digitalization and the digital economy in this case is dictated by the desire to understand the subject, including the term digital economy itself, and to give a meaningful forecast of the further development of the digital economy, based on long-term trends and on the fundamental properties of information presented in digital format. You should also pay attention to two different translations of the now popular term "digital economy". In one version of the translation, digital economy is a sector of the real economy, in another version,

digital economics is a scientific direction. In both cases, we are talking about digitalization, about the properties of information in digital format and its role in the economy, but still mixing of meanings is extremely undesirable. Therefore, sometimes English-language equivalents are used further (in parentheses). Another important feature for understanding the subject is the presentation of information in a binary calculus system that is convenient for machine reading and memorization. Without such a seemingly insignificant purely technical feature as a machine-readable form of information presentation, it might not make sense to talk about the digital economy (digital economy) in the absence of a subject for research and discussion.

Binary representation allows you to use a variety of physical principles for the representation, storage and transmission of information, repeatedly increasing the density of its recording and transmission speed. And this, in turn, opens up new prospects for the spread of digital technologies to all new sectors of the economy. For IT specialists, all this is meant as obvious, although it is almost never explicitly said. But you can often hear from economists that "the whole economy is numbers," and therefore the term "digital economy" does not make sense or has, but such as is convenient for them here and now. Such a misunderstanding is by no means uncommon, and therefore an explanation seems superfluous.

Of the fundamental properties of information in digital format, first of all, it is worth noting the possibility of copying and distributing it without loss of accuracy (bit by bit), as well as the idempotency of addition. In the simplest version it is . The flip side of the same property is the uncertainty of subtraction. In the language of economics, this means that information is uncompetitive in consumption, it does not disappear when consumed. In digital format, both of these

properties are especially pronounced precisely because the information is not distorted when transferred from one medium to another. But in economic theory and, especially, in mathematical models of the economy, non-competitiveness in consumption has always been absolute, or at least long before the appearance of the terms digital economy and digital economics. Moreover, long before the appearance of these terms, models of equilibrium (Arrow, 1962) and intersectoral balance of knowledge (Makarov, 1973) appeared, where knowledge was described as separate variables, and the addition of knowledge was idempotent. In the first case, it was Boolean addition, in the second, the maximum operation was used instead of the usual addition. We can even say that thanks to digitalization, the reality of knowledge representation has "caught up" with the models here. However, at the same time, the fact escapes the attention of the researcher that it was digitalization that ensured the accuracy of information transmission (bit to bit), and with it the opportunity to create many modern technologies, called "digital technologies" due to the use of digital representation of information in them. The institutional approach (Tapscott, 1995) makes it possible to compensate for this disadvantage by focusing on reducing transaction costs, but it overlooks the fundamental, primarily algebraic properties of information, and with them the opportunity to actively use mathematical models and make discoveries "at the tip of the pen", which, strictly speaking, is the mission of science.

A look at digitalization from positions spaced over time allows us to see features that usually escape the attention of those who write about it today, based only on modern experience and context. In particular, when considering the process of digitalization in retrospect, it is clearly seen how, as technologies using digital representation of information develop, they become more and more efficient

and economically profitable in comparison with analog technologies. At first, the digital format is justified only in exceptional cases. As a rule, this is due to communication systems and the secrecy of the transmitted information. Then there are digital electronic computers (digital computers). They are in demand for complex calculations in the space and nuclear industries. But, as it turns out, these machines are quite versatile, and therefore they are gradually replacing analog computers in other sectors of the economy. Digital format and digital technologies are rapidly taking over the entire media sphere, and then begin to penetrate into a variety of industries, including energy, construction and transport. Due to the reduction in the costs of searching for information and agreeing on the terms of contracts, new forms of business based on networks and digital technologies are emerging, and zealous heralds of change are already broadcasting that everything will change, "everything in general" (Koshelava, 2017). One might think that the long-awaited society of justice and universal prosperity on Earth is coming, or, on the contrary, the network dystopia from the novel (Pelevin, 2014) with all its dubious charms is coming to life.

There are also more restrained forecasts based on scientific theory. The most famous study of such a plan should be considered the book by Don Tapscott (Tapscott, 1995, 2014). Tapscott himself associates the appearance of the 2014 edition with the twentieth anniversary of its writing in its original version (1994) and the emergence of the term Digital Economy. Among the most important consequences of digitalization, Tapscott calls, referring to the theory of the firm of Ronald Coase (Coase, 1937)[1], the possibility of a radical reduction in transaction costs, primarily the costs of searching for information and concluding contracts, and as a consequence - the emergence of new forms of business, the exclusion of

intermediaries and direct interaction between the consumer and supplier. His main conclusion - the transfer of business from traditional firms to media - follows directly from the theory of Ronald Coase's firm. In addition, he points out many other changes in business and in life.

To give Tapscott his due, he approached the study from the standpoint of modern institutionalism and predicted almost all changes in business correctly. In particular, he noted the possible negative consequences of digitalization, subjecting the hypotheses put forward by him to a thorough theoretical analysis and justification based on the facts known by that time. And by the time the book was written, quite a lot of negative facts were known, primarily in the media economy (television, radio, cinema, press, etc.), where digitalization came relatively early. Here, digitalization and the emergence of the Internet have turned into an unprecedented surge in copyright and related rights violations ("piracy") with noticeable damage to copyright holders and investment losses for businesses in this sector of the economy. Of course, "piracy" and the associated investment losses could not remain without the attention of media economics researchers, they are quite well described in the economic literature, including those published before 1994, when the term digital economy did not exist yet.

Of course, Tapscott was not a pioneer in the study of media economics, as well as in the study of information economics, knowledge economics or knowledge management. However, he found a very good angle of view on all or almost all phenomena in different sectors of the economy related to digitalization, and proposed a new term that allows us to highlight the main thing that is happening in all these sectors of the economy today and the scientific directions focused on their study. Researchers working in each of them suddenly discover

that they have been engaged in the digital economy either in the sense of digital economy, creating and developing it as a new sector of the economy, or in the sense of digital economics, exploring the specific properties of the economy based on the knowledge presented today, usually in digital format. With such a broad approach to understanding the topic designated by the term "digital economy", the body of scientific publications on the digital economy turns out to be almost endless. Therefore, clarifications are needed.

To a lesser extent, they are required by the term "digital economy" in the sense of digital economy, since the development of any sector of the economy does not depend much on the word by which it is designated in scientific and not only scientific publications or official documents. The Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated May 9, 2017 No. 203 "On the Strategy for the development of the Information Society in the Russian Federation for 2017-2030" contains the following wording.

Digital economy is an economic activity in which the key factor of production is digital data, the processing of large volumes and the use of the results of analysis of which, compared with traditional forms of management, can significantly increase the efficiency of various types of production, technologies, equipment, storage, sale, delivery of goods and services.

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